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Optimized approach for determining the operating mode of pumps in networked operation

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Abstract. The work presents a refined method of determining the operating mode of pumps when working together on the network. The difference in the methodology is that the design of the drainage system takes into account the condition of the pipeline and the increase in local resistance due to siltation.

Keywords: network work, optimization, technology, efficiency, uncertainty.

Wastewater installations continue to be the largest consumers of electrical energy, the total costs of electricity supply to wastewater make up 25% of the total energy costs. Analysis of the work of coal mines in Ukraine showed that practically the entire nomenclature of mining equipment underwent modernization and not just once [1, 2, 3]. During the existence of the enterprise [4], the operating conditions of the equipment change many times, and very often, the required operating parameters differ significantly from those laid down during design [5, 6, 7].

The surface drainage of the "Dobropilska" mine was chosen as the research object (Fig. 1).

Figure 1
Diagram of the pumping station. "Dobropilska"

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During the operation of the ANC - 150/400 and NSV - 360/40 pumps, it became clear that they do not provide the specified passport performance [8, 9, 10].

In the process of work, measurements of productivity and pressure were made for four possible schemes of work (Table 1).

Table 1

**Operating characteristics of the pumps of the pumping station
sh. "Dobropilska"**

Parameter	Scheme of operation of the pumping station			
	One ANC pump	Parallel operation of ANC pumps	Sequential operation of two NSV pumps	Sequential operation of three NSV pumps
N, m	50	55	60	80
Q, m ³ /h.	250	270	280	320

Knowing the operating characteristics of the pumps, it is possible to determine the effective resistance of the pipeline a in m^5/s^6 ; by the formula:

$$a = \frac{H_c}{Q^2}, \quad (1)$$

where H_c is the pressure in the pipeline, m; Q - productivity, m³/hour;

Knowing the actual resistance of the pipeline, its diameter can be determined.

It is known that the resistance coefficient is determined by the formula [2]:

$$a = \frac{Z + \sum l_{\text{eKB}}}{3600^2 \cdot K^2} \quad (2)$$

Where Z is the length of the suction pipeline, m;

K^2 - the square of the flow characteristics of the pipeline;

$\sum l_{\text{eKB}}$ - length of equivalent resistances, m;

After performing the transformation of expression (2), we obtain:

$$a = \frac{Z + 0,177 \sum \xi \sqrt{\frac{Q_{\text{min}}}{\sqrt{i}}}}{3600^2 \cdot 576 \cdot d^{5,3}}, \quad (3)$$

where $\sum \xi$ - the sum of local resistance coefficients, based on

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*practice, 25–30 is accepted; $\Sigma \xi$
 \sqrt{i} – hydraulic slope;*

Based on expression (3), we will express the actual diameter of the pressure pipeline, it will be equal to:

$$d = \sqrt[5.3]{\frac{z + 0,177 \Sigma \xi \sqrt{\frac{Q_{\text{МНН}}}{\sqrt{i}}}}{3600^2 \cdot 576 \cdot a_{\text{д}}}} \quad (4)$$

After performing the calculations, it turned out that the actual diameter of the pressure pipeline decreased from 273 to 237 mm.

The obtained results indicate that in the course of work, the cross-section of the pipeline decreases over time, according to the research of A.D. Altschul, this process has an "avalanche-like" character [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20].

The amount of deposits significantly affects the reduction of the cross-section of the pipeline. With increased deposits, the resistance coefficient of the pipeline increases, so the pressure of the network also increases. The pressure characteristic of the network is equal to:., on the basis of this, we will plot the change in the characteristics of the pipeline over time (Fig. 2). $H = a \cdot Q^2$

Based on the real characteristics of the pipeline, it was found that the real mode of operation does not correspond to the theoretical one. Therefore, there was a need to develop a refined methodology that would take into account the increase in local resistances at the joints.

On the basis of experimental studies carried out by A.D. Altshul and V.M. Kalitsun, a dependence was established for determining the coefficient of increase in local resistances [5]:

$$K_c = 1 + \frac{\xi_c d}{\lambda l}, \quad (5)$$

where ξ_c – the contact coefficient was calculated by A.D. Altshul and V.M. Kalitsun;

d – nominal diameter of the pipeline;

λ – pipeline resistance coefficient;

l – the distance between the joints is equal to the standard

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length of the pipes, in accordance with GOST 8734-75, the length of the pipes is from 4 to 12.5 m;

- 1 - theoretical pressure characteristics of the pipeline;
- 2 - pressure characteristics of the pipeline after 5 years;
- 3 - pressure characteristics of the pipeline after 10 years;
- 4 - pressure characteristic after 15 years; 5 - pressure characteristics of the pipeline after 20 years

Figure 2

Change in pressure characteristics of the pipeline over time

A number of assumptions should be made when calculating the coefficient of local resistance increase:

from the practice of mine drainage, the average length of the pipes is 6 m;

hydraulic resistance will be calculated according to the formula [6]:

$$\lambda = 0,021d^{-0.3} \quad (6)$$

After performing the calculations, we will present in Table 2 the values of the coefficients of the increase of local resistances.

Table 2

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The value of the coefficient of increase of local resistance due to the joint for pipes with a diameter of up to 152 mm

d, mm	108	114	121	127	133	140	146	152
Ks	1,056	1,059	1,062	1,065	1,069	1,072	1,075	1,078

Table 3

The value of the coefficient of local resistance increase due to the joint for pipes with a diameter of more than 200 mm

d, mm	204	219	245	273	299	325	351	377	402	426
Ks	1,063	1,068	1,076	1,084	1,092	1,050	1,054	1,058	1,037	1,040

The calculated pipeline resistance increase factor has a number of advantages:

- ease of calculation;
- applicability for diameters from 100 to 800 mm;
- there is no "binding" to the increase in diameter;
- the values of the resistance coefficient are obtained as a result of research, and not by theoretical calculations;
- the possibility of using the "averaged" value in calculations regardless of the diameter;

Let's show in fig. 3 dependence of the resistance coefficient on the diameter, calculated according to expression (5).

Figure 3

Dependence of the resistance coefficient on the diameter

Taking into account the increase in network resistance

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over time, a new (refined) method of determining the operating mode of pumps when working together on the network was developed. The refined method of calculating the water discharge installation is based on the typical calculation method in accordance with SNIIP, taking into account the coefficient of increase in local resistances.

For pipelines in operation, it is necessary to determine the equivalent diameter of the pipeline based on measurements. The Darcy coefficient must also be calculated based on the equivalent diameter determined by the formula:

$$d_{\text{eKB}} = \sqrt[5,3]{\frac{L+0.177 \sum \xi \sqrt{\frac{Q_{\text{MIB}}}{\sqrt{l}}}}{3600^2 \cdot 576 \cdot a}} \quad (7)$$

Then the Darcy coefficient for pipelines in operation will be determined by the formula:

$$\lambda_{\text{eKB}} = 0,021 d_{\text{eKB}}^{-0.3} \quad (8)$$

In accordance with Shevelev's formula, the square of the pipe's divergence characteristic is determined by the formula:

$$K^2 = \frac{\pi^2 d^5 g}{8 \lambda} = 576 d^{5.3} \quad (9)$$

To determine the operating mode of the pump, it is necessary to plot the pressure characteristics of the pump and the pipeline on the same scale and in the common coordinate grid. The point of their intersection determines the operating mode.

When constructing the pressure characteristics of the pipeline, it is assumed that the diameter of the suction pipeline is equal to the diameter of the discharge pipeline.

Equation of the pressure characteristic for the accepted diameter of the pipeline:

$$H = H_r + a_p Q^2, \quad (10)$$

where H_r is the hydraulic resistance of the pipeline calculated

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according to the refined method $h^2/m-5$; it will be determined by the formula: a_p

$$a_p = a \cdot K_c \quad (11)$$

where a is the resistance coefficient of the pipeline determined by the formula: a

$$a = \frac{Z + \sum l_{\text{EKB}}}{3600^2 \cdot K^2} \quad (12)$$

K_s is the coefficient of increase in the resistance of the pipeline due to the joint, the values are given in Table 2, 3.

So, the method of determining the working mode is as follows:

- it is necessary to measure pressure and productivity in the operating pipeline;
- it is necessary to determine the equivalent diameter of the pipeline;
- on the basis of the equivalent diameter, determine the resistance coefficient of the pipeline;
- "adjust" the resistance coefficient of the pipeline by multiplying it by the coefficient of contact;
- build the characteristics of the network and the characteristics of the pumps - the intersection point will determine the operating mode.

The difference between this method and others is that the drainage system is not designed based on the selection of pumping equipment, but on the basis of the already existing drainage network.

The Darcy coefficient is calculated for pipes in operation, not for new ones. The calculated operating mode of the water discharge installation coincides with the nominal operating mode of the equipment. The resistance coefficient of the pipeline is determined by a simplified method and does not require detailed information on the drainage scheme. The calculation is based on the calculated pressure and productivity, not the nominal one, which significantly increases the accuracy of the calculations (Fig. 4).

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1 - pressure characteristics of the network calculated in accordance with SNIIP; 2 - the pressure characteristic of the network is calculated taking into account the equivalent diameter; 3 - the pressure characteristic of the network is calculated according to the specified method; 4 - pressure characteristic of one ANC pump; 5 - pressure characteristics of parallel working pumps of ANC; 6 - pressure characteristic of two sequentially operating pumps of the NSV; 7 - pressure characteristics of three sequentially operating pumps of the NSV

Figure 4

Determination of the operating mode during parallel and serial operation

As a result of the work, the main provisions for the development of a refined methodology were obtained, which were later confirmed experimentally:

- when calculating horizontal pipelines, the reduction of the pipeline cross-section due to the growth of deposits on the pipeline walls should be taken into account;
- the presence of joints serves as an additional source of local resistance;
- if it is possible to carry out preliminary measurements of supply and pressure, then the resistance coefficient should be calculated on the basis of the equivalent diameter.

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